

ROPE-LIKE DEFORMATION IN FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In theory, certain fibre composites may exhibit deformation which shows a transition between monolithic and rope-like behaviour at elevated temperatures. The characteristics of this form of deformation are investigated with reference to the results of experiments on a metal matrix composite.

INTRODUCTION

It is interesting to compare the properties of a rope with those of a monolithic material. Although a good quality rope may have a tensile strength as large as that of the monolithic material, the rope cannot support transverse loads unless tension is applied at the same time (Fig. 1). Indeed this inability to support shear forces or bending moments gives rope its unique qualities, i.e. enough flexibility for it to be bent and coiled with ease. On the other hand, the rope-like qualities can be made to vanish if the rope is soaked in resin and then cured, that is, the rope and cured resin together form a fibre composite. The interesting question is: what happens in the transition region where properties change from monolithic to rope-like? In fact, previous theoretical work has addressed this question¹⁻⁷ although there have been few experimental observations of the phenomenon.⁸ In this paper we report experimental observations of deformation in a metal matrix composite which show some of the characteristics of rope-like deformation. The deformation is analysed in a simple way and related to some of the previous theoretical findings.

Fig 1. Comparison and rope-like behaviour under transverse loads

Fig 2. Effect of temperature on the strength of fibres (ceramic) and matrix (metal or thermoplastics).

DEFORMATION MECHANISM

In essence a rope behaves in the way indicated above for two reasons: (i) the diameter of the fibres are small relative to the overall diameter of the rope; (ii) individual fibres are free to slide relative to their neighbours, limited only by the friction between them. On the other hand, if the fibres were bonded to a matrix the behaviour would change to an extent which depends on the shear strength of the matrix, τ_0 . Obviously, when τ_0 is large enough the composite behaves like a monolithic solid, albeit an orthotropic one, but as $\tau \rightarrow 0$ the behaviour must go through a transition, moving towards pure rope-like behaviour when $\tau_0 = 0$. In practice we might expect this transition to occur in metal-matrix or thermoplastic matrix composites with ceramic fibres at high temperatures, simply because the strength of the matrix falls with increasing temperature as illustrated in Fig 2. At the outset of this work we considered the question: under what circumstances could large-scale deformation be observed in a unidirectional fibre composite at temperatures below the melting point of the matrix. Before considering the experimental results, however, it is worth examining the nature of the deformation in question.

Fig 3. Illustration of the nature of rope-like deformation: (a) lamellae, (b) individually bent and (c) welded together; (d) continuum composed of laminae of infinitesimal thickness bent to the arc of a circle, the shear strain is equal to the angle θ .

case the shear strain γ in the deformed section is equal to the angle θ , i.e. γ is zero at the centre section and increases linearly with angle θ to a maximum at the edges AB and CD (Fig 3). The stresses in the section are characterised by a shear stress, s , a hydrostatic pressure, p , and a tensile stress T . To solve for the stresses p and T some assumption must be made about s . The simplest is that the matrix is rigid-plastic so that $s = \tau_0$ after finite deformation. Relations of the following form are then obtained

$$p = \tau_0 f \tag{1}$$

A process of bending is illustrated schematically in Fig 3. In this we consider a number of laminae bent individually to a series of arcs then welded together after bending (a-c). This operation shows that were the same deformation to be achieved in the laminate rather than in the separated laminae considerable slip would be required between their surfaces. It is a simple matter to pass to the limit and consider the solid to be composed of an infinite number of infinitesimal laminae. The most elementary set of characteristics which could then be assigned to the material are those of an incompressible continuum, inextensible in the fibre direction with a well defined shear strength τ_0 . The mechanics of this sort of material have been studied in theory over the last twenty years²⁻⁷ following on from the model of Adkins and Rivlin.¹ The theory has been called the theory of ideal fibre-reinforced materials (IFRM). Without referring to the complexities of the mathematics needed to handle finite deformation, we now summarize the relevant results of IFRM theory as applied to the bent section illustrated in Fig 3.

To arrive at a solution in IFRM theory it is first necessary to impose a given deformation on a shape with a specified materials orientation, e.g. a flat bar bent to the arc of a circle. The rules for the kinematics of all possible deformations have been given by Rogers and Pipkin,³ but in the present, simple

$$T = \tau_0 g + \tau_0 h. \text{ (surface singularity term)} \quad (2)$$

where f , g and h are dimensionless functions of deformation, position and specimen dimensions. These terms are of order unity, so p and the first term in T in (2) are of the same order of magnitude as τ_0 . The second term in T contains a singularity which occurs on the boundaries AD and BC (Fig 3), described by the dirac delta function, i.e. infinite anywhere on AC or BC and zero elsewhere. Singular boundary stresses are a common feature of IFRM theory. An alternative interpretation of the singular stresses is possible,^{4,8} taking account of the finite diameters of the fibres in real composites. Nevertheless large stresses are expected to develop at the surface.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Specimens of an Al₂O₃/Magnesium Alloy (Fiber FP in ZE41A) unidirectional composite containing 50 volume percentage of fibre were tested. An attempt was made to bend initially flat bars (35x12.5x2.5 mm) over a semicircular former without causing catastrophic fracture. This proved to be rather difficult to achieve, but after some experimentation it was found that the specimens could be deformed around a semicircular former with a radius of 25 mm provided that the deformation occurred slowly at elevated temperatures. To achieve this deformation, specimens were loaded initially in three-point bending, the point of contact with the former being placed mid-way between the support rollers (see inset in Fig 4(a)). The bending rig was placed in a furnace at 300 C and loaded through a lever arm with a constant force. As large scale deformation developed the specimen collapsed to the form imposed by the former (inset in Fig 4(a)) and this process was monitored by recording the displacement of the lever arm as a function of time.

Fig 4. Results of deformation of Al₂O₃ composites at 300°C: (a) creep curves obtained by bending specimens over a semi-circular former, S is the applied shearing force per unit cross-sectional area. (b) photograph of a specimen after deformation.

Since the geometry of the arrangement is fixed the maximum shear in the specimen (defined in the previous section) can be expressed as in terms of the displacement. Thus, the creep curves shown in Fig 4(a) were obtained from the displacement-time data. The curves shown are for different applied shearing forces, expressed as shearing force per unit cross sectional area, S . At first the creep rate was small, but after a period of time which increased with decreasing S , the creep was found to accelerate and in this stage the specimen deformed rapidly to the final shape determined by the former. The process of deformation was found to be

very sensitive to the value of the applied load; large scale deformation occurred within 1000s with $S > 12.0$ MPa, but no large-scale deformation occurred with $S = 9.0$ MPa within this time-scale. An example of one of the heavily deformed specimens is shown in the photograph in Fig 4(b).

Microcracking. Although we were able to deform specimens without catastrophic fracture, it is not surprising to find that specimens are internally cracked after what, for a composite material, is extensive deformation. Fibre fracture was observed, mainly at the specimen surface, as shown in the micrograph in Fig 5(a). In addition, fibre-matrix debonding and shear cracking was observed in the centre sections of the specimen (Fig 5(b)). Note the curvatures of the fibres which are evident in Fig 5, illustrating that deformation has in fact occurred by the rope-like deformation mechanism described above.

Fig 5. Examples of microcracking observed in sections of a composite after deformation: (a) fibre fracture near surface layer, (b) shear microcracks observed at the centres of the section.

DISCUSSION

Rope-like deformation of composites will be familiar to anyone with experience of the lay-up of pre-impregnated composites with resin matrices, where the matrix is in effect a viscous fluid. Similarly, rope-like deformation occurs to advantage in the fabrication of thermoplastic composites at temperatures above the melting point of the matrix. In contrast to these examples we have investigated deformation of a composite at temperatures below the melting point of the matrix. Here the deformed shape is obtained by the same process of relative sliding of the fibres but the resistance to shear of the matrix is very much larger. The effect of this difference can be gauged qualitatively using eqns. 1 and 2. If τ_0 is infinitesimally small, as with a fluid, the stresses p and T are also small to the same order. If however τ_0 is finite the other stresses are scaled accordingly and, of these, the singular term in T in (2) is the most significant. Thus the large surface stresses⁸ probably account for the fibre cracking exemplified in Fig 5(a). On the other hand, shear cracking is observed in the centre sections as in Fig 5(b) and this cannot be explained on a stress criterion of microcracking because according to (1) there is a hydrostatic *pressure* in this region. Most likely, the generation of shear microcracks is a strain controlled phenomenon and the presence of a preexisting defect is required to explain their occurrence. Finally we note that the application of eqns. 1 and 2 to the experimental observations is an approximate procedure since the deformation was produced by time-dependent plastic shear. The time-dependent problem is a good deal more complicated to understand in detail and is currently under investigation by the authors, using finite element methods.

Applications. Given the fact that the alumina fibres are intrinsically brittle and that the bond between fibres and the matrix is relatively weak even in the best composites, it is surprising that large scale deformation can be achieved at a temperature only two thirds of the melting point of the matrix. However, well-developed, rope-like deformation is likely to be a rare occurrence in practice with fracture intervening before large-scale deformation can be observed. Nonetheless, the basic process of thermally activated matrix shear is important in composites for loadings other than simple tension. To this end, theoretical and experimental study of other aspects of the phenomenon, including time-dependent fracture and buckling collapse is being undertaken in the authors' laboratories.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors wish to thank DuPont de Nemours and Co. Ltd. for their support of this work. One of the authors (WN) acknowledges with gratitude the support of the British Council.

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